

**ASPECTS OF FOREIGN ALBANOLOGISTS
CONTRIBUTION IN THE STUDY OF THE
PRIZREN AND SURROUNDINGS FOLK
SPOKEN ALBANIAN**

Linguistics

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Abstract

In addition to some language studies, of 1902 it was published a Serbo - Croatian Dictionary, with about 4, 000 words and 1187 questions - answers, but the language of the vocabulary prompted the linguists. H. Agani in the Study: What is the linguistic sphere of L. Kujunxhiq's Dictionary, in 1954, featured the mistakes which in this dictionary misinformed even the well-known linguists. The influence of the Albanian language made Rahovec Serbo-Croatian, a mixed language, while the lexis of the vocabulary includes the Rahovec / Orahovac folk, that of the city of Prizren and that of the city of Gjakova. Here we have the passage in a, u to u in suffixes - type and - level, the use of ll in place of dh, the decline of h hover etc. In recognition of these talk, they are distinguished by N. Jokli, J. Thumanne, H. Pedersen, G. Vajgandi etc., though the recognition of the Albanian language in the previous situation was the most important. S. Mladenovi visited the area between Prizren and Pristina in 1925, publishing the article: Remarks on Albanians and Albanian in Northern Macedonia and Old Serbia. Later, M. Lambretzi will give some features of the dialects of eastern Gegese, which also includes the dialects of the city of Prizren. Foreign Albanians lacked the knowledge of the Albanian language, while some Slavic scholars had hegemonic purposes, such as: M. Pavlovic and G. Elezović etc.

Introduction

According to the aspect of studying dialects in Albanian, in this context and of the verbal dialects of the northern dialect, which also includes the Prizren and surrounding neighborhoods, Albanian linguistics have achieved important, though not enough, results. The domain of the dialectal material study obviously cannot be separated from the proper conditions and opportunities, because there were some better conditions of investigation and somewhere there was not. This primarily means the material investigated in the early stages, and the studies vary considerably, not only in terms of results but also in the methodology used¹. In this curriculum, Prizren and surroundings studies have been enriched², even with a monograph, above Hasi³ folks, for Anadrin's⁴ talk, then special scientific papers for Kabashi's talk of Prizren⁵, Zhur's⁶ talk of Prizren, the speaker of the city⁷ of Prizren⁸, the area of Prizren⁹ Mountains in Vërrin.

¹ Beci, B. “Të folmet veriperëndimore të shqipes dhe sistemi fonetik i së folmes së Shkodrës”, Tiranë, 1995, f. 9.

² Ajeti, Idriz: “Studime Gjuhësore në Fushën të Shqipes”, I, Prishtinë, Rilindja, 1989.

³ Badallaj, Imri: “E folmja e Hasit”, Prishtinë, 2001.

⁴ Pajaziti, Naser: “E folmja e Anadrinit”, Prishtinë 2008.

⁵ Halimi, M. “E folmja e Kabashit të Prizrenit”, “Kërkime. Dialektologjike.”, Prishtinë, 1985.

⁶ Badallaj, Imri: “Disa veçori fonetike të së folmes së Zhurit” GJASSHF, V-1975, Prishtinë. 1976; “Nyjat në të folmen e Vërrinit”, Seminari i XXI Ndërkombëtar për GJLKSH, Prishtinë, 2002.

⁷ Topçiu, Vedita: “Veçoritë fonetike të së folmes së elemntit katolik të qytetit të Prizrenit”, Punim i mbrojtur i Magjistraturës në FF të UP në Degën e Gjuhës shqipe, Prishtinë, 1988.1978.

⁸ Topalli, Mehmet: “Sistemi fonetik i të folmes shqipe të qytetit të Prizrenit”, FF i UP, Dega e Gjuhës shqipe, Prishtinë, 1980.

⁹ Zymberi, Abdullah: “Sistemi foljor në të folmen e fshatit Struzhë të Malësisë së Prizrenit”, SNGJLKSH, 2. Prishtinë, 1978.

It is also worth mentioning the study imitations which distinguish the first beginnings of the dialectal¹⁰ identification of the dialects, but in this aspect a good work has been done in the collection of the lexicons¹¹ of these tales and the compilation of dictionaries dialectics¹². Undoubtedly, on the basis of the overall success of the studies in these areas, the ADGJSH¹³ is also the leader of these achievements.

Methodology

To give a more inclusive picture of the contribution of foreign albanologists to the study of the Prizren folk talk and its surroundings, I first approached dialectical studies of the Prizren townships: monographs, works of art, dictionary dialects of rare words of popular vocabulary, then theoretical views as well as observations of the lexical description of these city and Prizren districts. Since Prizren and also the Prizren area have a very important and sensational story in terms of the Albanian element, even in a highly recognizable way, we would add to it, not only in terms of the Albanian element, since this environment has all too been a foothold of all other social and cultural activities in the region. In many cases, large movements have been modified and directed, which have been associated with notable impact on the region, such as the Albanian League of Prizren and so on. In the context of the treatment of this study paper, although no comparative linguistic¹⁴ approaches have been observed, as the theoretical attempts of the object and the methods¹⁵ of study in these areas of the Prizren and surroundings¹⁶ contexts.

The writings of the past centuries has helped a lot to follow the beginning of the development of various dialectical phenomena. In the context of the Kosovo Talks, apart from the work of P. Bogdan "The Chetnik of the Prophets", "The Christian Doctrine" of Gj. N. Kazazai, "Vebihjes" by T. Boshnjak and "Divani" by Sheh Maliqi, a good effort that has helped to give a fuller description of the phonetics and phonological features and to identify the reflection of the development of various not-linguistic occurrences of the Prizren and surrounding areas is the "Serbo-Croatian Dictionary", published in 1902, by author L. Kujunxhiqin. In this context linguistic is the content of the Serbo-Croatian vocabulary of L. Kujunxhiq. The collected linguistic material divides it into two pillars that capture about four thousand words and words, where are given the days, the seasons of the month, the sides of the world, the numerals, while on the last pages are added exercises to learn the language of speech with 1187 questions and answers compiled with simple sentences and extended sentences.

¹⁰ Bardhi, Medi: "Disa veçori karakteristike në vokalizimin e së folmes së Hasit" SGJ, II, (Dilektologji), Prishtinë, 1979; Luboteni, G. "Ndryshimet më të qensishme dialektore ndërmjet gegnishtes dhe toskënishtes", "Përparimi", X, Prishtinë, 1960, f. 77.

¹¹ Topalli, M. " Fjalë e shprehje të rralla të shqipes", "Jehona", Shkup, 6/1978, XVI;

¹² Zymberi, Abdullah: "Fjalor i fjalëve të rralla", Prishtinë, 1979; Zymberi, Abdullah: "Fjalor popullor: me rreth 20000 fjalë", "Grafbeni", Prishtinë, 2014, f. 12; „Nga leksiku i Hasit të Prizrenit“; „Toponimia e fshtrave Kojush dhe Plane“; „Toponimia fshatit Mazrek“, „Gjurmime albanologjike“ V-75, Prishtinë, 1976, f. 79.

¹³ ASHSH IGJL "Atlasi Dialektologjik i Gjuhës Shqipe", Universiteti degli Studi di Napoli L'Orientale, Itali, Vëllimi i I-rë, 2007; Vëllimi i II-të 2008, f. 9.

¹⁴ Badallaj, Imri: "Format e kohës së ardhme të shqipes krahasuar me ato të serbishtes", "Seminari i XVIII Ndërkombëtar për gjuhën, letërsinë dhe kulturën shqiptare", Prishtinë, 1996; Blaku, MURAT: "Ndikimi i shqipes mbi të folmen serbe të Kosovës", GJASSHF, 23-1993, Prishtinë, 1994. 24-1994, Prishtinë, 1995, f. 66.

¹⁵ Badallaj, Imri: "Probleme të objektit dhe të metodës në studimin e dialektologjisë", "Filologji", nr. 1, Prishtinë, 1996, f. 87.

¹⁶ Pajaziti N., "E folmja e Anadrinit", Prishtinë, 2008, f. 21.

However, the question of which spheres of speech is the language of this vocabulary, added the interest of dialectologists. It is for this reason that the researcher, H. Agani, of the Serbian-Albanian Dictionary of L. Kujunxhiç will be approached to examine it in his 300-page monograph.

Encouraged by linguistic curiosity, H. Agani, this view will for the first time reveal in his diploma work: "Some Phonetic and Morphological Features of Gjakova Folk," in 1954. The above-mentioned doubt will justify by specifying more precisely the linguistic area of L. Kujunxhiç's Dictionary in the study: "What Is the Language Language of the L. Kujunxhiç Dictionary", published in two parts in the journal "Albanian Alumni Research". In this respect, the author of the monograph giving information to the author, the publication of the work also includes a number of mistakes that L. Kujunxhiç did in writing the various terms of the words, which also misinformed a number of well-known linguists, who for explanations of phenomena different languages selected examples from this Glossary. From the detailed treatment that makes our researcher Kujunxhiç vocabulary outlines the opinion that the influence of the Albanian probably made the Rahovec Serb - Croat "mixed language"¹⁷. In determining the linguistic context of this Dictionary, F. Dulaj, based on the studies of Ajah and H. Agani as well as the study of Rahovec / Orahovac folk spoken language that the issue for these talk can only be accepted as partial¹⁸.

The study, "What is the language of the Dictionary of L. Kujunxhiçit" by H. Agan, examines the sound system in phonetics, the aspects of the grammatical categories in the field of morphology: the name, the verb etc., and then the same ones comparing them data of authors of these sides, such as: P. Bogdan, Gj. N. Kazazi, T. Boshnjak, and Sheh Maliqi, respectively, fights a considerable number of dialectical phenomena with distinct values between the northeastern geghe's speech and with a special emphasis on the spheres of the Prizren and its surroundings. Further on, in this regard, the author concludes that the Glossary of Lubomir Kujunxhiç reflects the Albanian of a wide area that catches the Rahovec folk, then the city of Prizren's talk with that of the Catholic element of this city, and in cases of especially with certain elements of the folk of the city of Gjakova¹⁹ ".

From the apparent phenomena it is known that the passage of a (master, ornar), to u in the suffixes -your and -leaf (ijum, axhamilluk), the use of the vowel u and i instead of thaty: (babaxhush, cumur²⁰, jumbo, jail, bilmel, hizmet) etc. Further, in this regard, the use of ll in place of dh, the fall of the faring h h in the three positions of the word, the non-separation in the writing of the consonants, because in Rahovec only r, or any other element²¹ is heard. While in the field of morphology marks the points of contact with the vocabulary of the Dictionary with Rahovec's folk talks: the plural of names (atkinj, podkon), the use of the first-

¹⁷ Agani, H. "Cila është treva gjuhësore e Fjalorit të L. Kujunxhiçit", "GJASSHF", 1, 2 1969, Prishtinë, f. 54.

¹⁸ Dulaj, F. "E folmja e Rahovecit me rrethinë", Prishtinë, 2016, f. 296.

¹⁹ Gosturani, XH. "Dr. Hilmi Agani, Fjalori i Lubomir Kujunxhiçit", Prishtinë, 1981, f. 380, "Studime Filologjike", nr. 4, 1988, Tiranë, f. 159.

²⁰ Dulaj, F. "E folmja e Rahovecit me rrethinë", Prishtinë, 2016, f. 95.

²¹ Agani, H. "Fjalori i Lubomir Kujunxhiçit", Prishtinë, 1981, f. 93.

person singular variant in several verbs with the theme in consonant and voices of the subject that is exchanged (I speak, I take) etc.

In describing the subject matter of the Dictionary, with all the errors that have been reflected in the treatment of the content of the word, the aspects of the phenomena that have been examined, their accuracy, the expectation to express consideration for the time or a line of language treatments between these, even though this is a bit modest. On the other hand H. Agan's monograph: Lubomir Kujunxhiç's Dictionary passes through the field of dialectology and Albanian lexicography by bringing elements and inputs to the study of the northeastern geghe group, namely their observation without entering into the deep analysis structure of the talk of the Prizren area with the surroundings as well as the related tales that define the areas of these areas, such as that of Gjakova as well as that of Rahovec's folk.

The literary search for Albanian dialectology begins in the middle of the nineteenth century, when the curiosity of foreign linguists awakens, among which we can mention, first, the pervasive investigations of German linguists. N. Jokli²², the first step in the recognition of the tales of this area, has paid special attention to the Albanian language system in terms of historical development, and in 1915 published the "Temporary Notice for Northeastern Gaelic Dialect Studies made at the commission of the Balkan Commission of the Imperial Academy of Sciences in Vienna²³".

Then in this regard, in the research on the literature of the peoples of Eastern Europe, J. Thumanne Research on the history of the peoples of Eastern Europe, published in Leipzig (1774), especially in the chapter dealing with history and language of Albanians distinguished in order, right Albanian language and people: descendants of Illyria and Illyricum.

But in this furrow of this likewise reflection will act Vajgandi²⁴ (G.Weigand), Jokli, Lambreci, although "the recognition of the Albanian language in the then state of affairs seems to be more important and more urgent for the scientists who lack of sufficient linguistic resources made comparative studies of language, so very little was devoted attention to the philological issues of language and especially its dialectology²⁵". In the context of the treatment of the Albanian consonants that are part of these speeches, namely the opinions expressed by the linguists Meyer, Miletiq and others.

²² Norbert, Jokl: "Beitrage albanischen Grammatik", I, IF, 30, 1912, II., 36, 1916.

²³ Jokl, N. "Vorläufiger Bericht über die im Auftrag der Balkan- Kommission der Kais Akad. Der Wis", in Wien. Phil-hist Kl. , 52, 1915. IG.Von Hahn: "Albanische studien", Jena, 1954.

²⁴ Weigand, G. "Der Gegische Dialekt von Borgo Erizzo bei Zara in Dalmatien, Jahresbericht des Instituts für Rummanische Sprache", Leipzig, 1911, f.17.

²⁵ Ajeti, I. "Vepra", I, Prishtinë, 1997, ASHAK, f. 9.

About the existence of loneliness in Albanian language

I Ajeti on the basis of Holger Pedersen's thoughts will address the varieties of these phonemes in his study: "Types of l in Albanian dialects of Brisk-Shestan Krajë "from which will result the study, that in the Albanian language are merged two types of habitual phonemes: ll ll²⁶. According to the Southeastern Europe, a number of linguists, mostly Slavic, who, in recognition of the various Balkan disciplines, also show the considerations for the recognition of the Albanian language. Among them are J. Kopitari, and later, his student, the Slovenian, F. Miklosic for the reflection efforts in the volume: "Albanian Language Research" (1870). Furthermore, H. Baric distinguishes considerations for Albanian language and culture by supporting the fair view that the inner issue in Albanian²⁷ is an underlying process of the Albanian language, in the volume "The Hymns in the History of the Albanian Language". But contrary to this right opinion, there were also linguists that the extension of the nose-length phenomena in the gege dialect have been prominent borrowed from the Romanian language, such as A. Balota²⁸. Also in this context with regard to the issue of nose-length, I. Badallaj, in the monograph "Has's Talk", states that V. Cimohovsky's opinion should not be perceived that nose vowels always come out long: "in it Has's talk, but also in some other gegely tales, some nose vowels are pronounced with short lengths: one"²⁹ etc.

The Bulgarian scientist S. Mladenov has made efforts to recognize this area. In August and early September 1916, Mladenov visited North Macedonia and in particular the area between Prizren and Pristina, he selected dialectical subjects in these cities and in the surrounding areas. In 1925, he published the article: "Remarks on Albanians and Albanians in Northern Macedonia and Old Serbia". The article deals with some of the main phonetic features of the spoken Albanian language of the surroundings of Kaçanik / Kačanik, Tetovo and some other suburbs, but with a shallow reliability. "I think that the study of Sofia Slavlav, Mladenov, is a glimpse of the depth and the necessary recognition, countries and countries, focusing on the general features of the Macedonian and Kosovo Albanian spoken language without being put in focusing the main features of the talents, we know nothing about the volume and quality of vowels, nor even their nose intonation"³⁰.

In the article *Issues of the development of literary Albanian in Kosovo*, published in the fourth volume of SNGJLKSH (1995), the author, F. Raka, quite rightly selects a more complex effort on some phonetic features, such as: the good of the nozzle came from all over the ears of the eastern³¹ gege, then about the morphological characteristics and any other lexical note of C. Tagliavini in the work: "The Albanian dialects of the type of eastern gege (Dardania and

²⁶ Badallaj, Imri: "E folmja e Hasit", Prishtinë, 2001, f. 90.

²⁷ Bariç, H. "Hymje në historinë e gjuhës shqipe", Prishtinë, 1955, f. 68.

²⁸ Balota, A. "La nasalisation et le rhotacism dans les langues roumaine et albanaise", Bukuresti, 1925, f. 24.

²⁹ Badallaj, I. "E folmja e Hasit", Prishtinë, 2001, f. 31.

³⁰ Ajeti, Idriz: "Studime Gjuhësore në Fushën të Shqipësisë", I, Prishtinë, "Rilindja", 1989, f. 19.

³¹ C. Tagliavini: "Studime gjuhësore" I (dialektologji), *Të folmet shqipe të tipit të gegërishtes verilindore*, IAP, Prishtinë, 1978, f. 139.

northwestern Macedonia), published , in 1942, where it is important to distinguish the eastern geg from Kosovo, which belong to the central³² gege spoken language.

Nevertheless, in this context, Karl Taliavini himself (C. Tagliavini) will clearly state: "Our research, of course, has a completely temporary character as it is based on press material which as an old existing one, is poor and of different value. It can be said with certainty that the data of "Albanian Language Linguistic" can significantly modify the conclusions of our study, which is strictly limited to the requirement of material to give some phonetic characteristics of the eastern geges, marking only some morphological features as well as any lexicon"³³.

Further, in this context, C. Tagliawin's findings as well as M. Lambrec's findings that the dialects of the western provinces of Macedonia are included in a group of Kosovo's belonging to the eastern group of Northern Gegevere will be expressed by B. Beci³⁴. Six years later, M.Lambretzi³⁵, speaking of the dialects of the Albanian language, will try to give some characteristics of the dialects of the eastern gege (Peja, Deçan, Gjakova, Prizren, Tetovo, Vrapcis, Gostivar, Galiçnik, Debar, Vucitrn, Prishtina, Skopje), but will not leave within the data of K.Taliavinit.Natyrisht that besides these reflections we will have estimates that still to this day, so for example is the opinion of the linguist Burgman, who scientifically argues the existence of a descriptive way in all the Indo-European languages, "or as he said in the Indo-European languages," will be specified by I. Badallaj in the monograph on Hasa's language when it deals with the development of the history of the exclamation manner³⁶.

The first stage of tracing dialectal studies, as it is seen and is characterized, by J. Gjinari has been expressed in the volume "Dialectology", it is identified the lack of proper studies of the northeastern gege, of the talk of the city of Prizren and its surroundings. Although it would be completely unforgivable if we did not appreciate the help of the studies of this stage for signaling some phonetic, morphological and lexical features originally made by these foreign authors. Yes, however, we must underline the overwhelming opinion supported by many authors in this regard that foreign scholars lacked the broadest knowledge of the Albanian language in general, because a number of those, such as Erdeljanovic, defined our ethnicity even as Macedonians of Macedonia ("Makedonski Serb", 1920). But in particular, they lacked the knowledge of the folk talk that sometimes they had as object for study and M. Begolli would point out when it comes to Rugova's speech in the magazine "Progress" (1958).

Nevertheless, as we have above pointed out, "we will find the beginnings of foreign scholars who have done this work, either by chance or by other means, by the study of the

³² Beci, B. "Mbi katër inovacione fonetike të të folmeve të Gegërisë së Mesme", "Konf. e parë e Studimeve Albanologjike", 15-21 nëntor 1962, Tiranë, 1965, f. 261.

³³ Tagliavini, C. "Le parlate albanesi di tipo glego orientale [Dardania e Macedonia nord occidentale]": në „La terra albanese redenta”, "Kosovo", Roma, 1942, f.19-8o.

³⁴ Beci, Bahri: "Të folmet qendrore të gegërishtes", DSH, V, Tiranë, 1987, f. 7.

³⁵ Lambertz, M. "Albanische Lesebuch", I, Teil, Gramatik und albanische Texte, Leipzig, 1948, f. 9.

³⁶ Badallaj, Imri: "E folmja e Hasit", Prishtinë, 2001, f. 186.

Albanian language and its dialects. These were the words of Bahri Beci when speaking during the developments of linguistic research in the province of Mat of the Republic of Albania³⁷.

In this regard, even those few attempts have been made without a dialectical sound basis, i.e. they have been based on notes that have been based on research done on the occasion of a trip, folkloric and here too by the old authors of our literature. The inaccuracy of this collected data will also make Kujundzic's Dictionary of Albanian to consider as well-known Albanians of Gjakova, as well as prominent Albanians such as Jokli, Çabej, Taljiavini and so on. Also disagreeing with the view that the study of the structure of Albanian by some Slavic scholars of the time was made to bring about meaningful thoughts and thoughts on the history of the Albanian language, mainly hegemonic, such as M. Pavlovic and G. Elezović³⁸.

And not only this last one, who will go even further by "discovering" that Albanians came to Kosovo and Western Macedonia only after the XVII century, because there were no Albanian names in Albania. Thoughts that were arguably argued by Albanian science and our scientists in the First Assembly of Illyrian Studies would E. Çabej, conclude precisely about the problem of the Albanian language formation site in this context³⁹.

Dialectical data reinforces even more the autochthony of the Albanian element from the earliest times, in the entire ethnographic set of Albanian speaking coexisting varieties of the Prizren and its surroundings: Gjonaj, Marash, Sharr, Lumbardh, Therrand, giving base to scientific identification of autochthonous toponym of Albanian⁴⁰ nature: Naisus - Nishi, Scupi - Skopje, Ulpiana - Lipjani etc.

In spite of the results even today, there are no "circles and true scientists" that Albanians and Albanians do not accept as genuine followers of the Illyrians and of the Illyrian followers, even at the level of academics: M. Garashanini, F , Papazogullu, V. Popovic, etc., ignoring the reality of autochthonous analysis, scientific methodology, and in this context neither murderous means, nor forms of murder: "... in a dark street of Zagreb were killed by iron poles the Yugoslav scholar, Milan Shuflain ... "will add the main figure of Albanian letters, Ismail Kadare, to the victim of serbo-hegemonic⁴¹ appetites.

On the eve of the last war in Kosovo, and in this regard from the "science" of the ASHA of Serbia, for the "multiethnicity" of our city, SC Nikolic will come up with frustrating information that the town of Prizren is made up of Muslims: Turks, Muslim Muslims, and Albanians, while Christians: Serbs, Greeks, Vlachs, Albanians, etc., were a minority⁴² !?

In the face of all these life challenges, the dialectological studies have resulted in exhaustive reflections of which is certainly the dialectical atlas of the Albanian language

³⁷ Beci, Bahri: "Hulumtime gjuhësore në Mat", BUSHSSHSH, nr. 2, 1962, dhe 2, 1963, f. 29.

³⁸ Ajeti, I. "Mendime të studiuesve jugosllavë për historinë e gjuhës shqipe", GJA, 20-90, Prishtinë, 1991, f. 13.

³⁹ Çabej, E. "Problemi i vendit të formimit të gjuhës shqipe", "Kuvendi i parë i st. Ilire", II, Tiranë, 1972, f. 7

⁴⁰ Çabej, E. "Problemi i autoktonisë së shqiptarëve ë dritën e emrave të vendeve", BUSHT, Tiranë, II, 1958.

⁴¹ Ismajli, R. "Dr. M. Shuflay – viktimë e apetiteve hegjemoniste", "Bota e re", nr. 36, Prishtinë, f. 13.

⁴² Nikoliq, Serafim S.: "Prizren od srednjoveka do savremenog doba", ASHAS, Prizren, 1998, f. 430.

(ADGJSH), and in this result of this multi-year work, however, this region is also an integral part of the presentation of seven hundred maps processed with aspects of emptying the most tangible⁴³ language issues.

Conclusion

Meetings of nations have not always been desirable and welcomed. The toponymical as well as the anthroponymy of the city's squares of Prizren and its surroundings belong directly to the extension of the ancient Dardania, while this space also directly reflects the Illyrian Region, Illyria, and as a consequence of this is part of the Illyrian anthroponymy by the well-known Illyrian origin of the Dardanian tribe. In the urban areas of the city of Prizren and its surroundings, as well as in the other tales of Kosovo's and Balkan speaking spheres, there are also a small number of linguistic communities that speak Turkish, i.e. Turkish, or Bosnian (Serbian) in their language use today. Such linguistic communities are in the very center of the city of Prizren as well as in the surroundings.

Regarding to the contribution of foreign albanologists to the Albanian language that we have listed on the pages of this short overview, we note that Albanian linguistics in terms of the study of Albanian dialects, in this context also of verbal dialects of the northern dialect, where Prizren's dialects and the surroundings have important results. The first days in the recognition of the Albanian dialectics subject study began in the mid-nineteenth century, in this context of the city of Prizren and its surroundings are foreign linguists, such as N. Jokli, S. Mladenov, G. Weigand, H. Pedersen, M. Lambreci, C. Tagliavini, H. Bariq, etc.

In this aspect, even those few efforts that have been made have had no good dialect basis because they have been based on research done on the occasion of any trip, from folk, and here also from the old authors of our literature. These data will also make prominent albanologists such as Jokli, Çabej and Taljiavini inaccurate in reflecting the examples obtained from Kujunxhiq's Dictionary.

The study of the structure of Albanian language by some Slavic scholars of the time has been done in order to bring distorted thoughts and statements to the history of the Albanian language, mainly in the function of hegemonic goals, such as M. Pavlovic and G. Elezović.

The approximate dialectal features that are distinguished in the phonetic, phonological and grammatical system of these Prizren and surrounding circles with their neighboring cultures with all their main features are considered to be the result of long contacts of speakers of this area, of course without excluding here also the specific influences in the peripheral and especially transitional dialects, such as from Luma, Rahovec and etc.

⁴³ Shkurtaj, GJ. "Dialektet e shqipes", Tiranë, 2012, f. 163.

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